

**PATTERNS OF CARDIOTHORACIC DISEASES AND
PROCEDURES IN PAKISTAN**Dr Bilal Zaib¹, Dr Suhaib Ali Khan¹, Dr Awais Nawaz Khan¹¹Ayub Medical College, Abbottabad

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Abstract:

Introduction: Cardiovascular, heart valve and congenital heart diseases (CHD) constitute a major part of adult and pediatric diseases. **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the patterns of cardiothoracic diseases and procedures in Pakistan. **Material and methods:** This descriptive study was conducted in Ayub medical college during June 2019 to December 2019. Collecting patients' data was conducted through interviewing the patients included in the study and reviewing their medical files. A predesigned questionnaire was used for data collection, and included inquiries about socio-demographic data of the studied patients, smoking, types of cardiovascular diseases and thyroid dysfunction among them. **Results:** The data was collected from 180 patients. There were more females than males. The patients who were younger than 60 years old represented 39.2% of the study population. More than one-third of the individuals (34.3%) were between 60 and 70 years of age, 19.9% were between 70 and 80 years of age, and only 6.6% were older than 50 years. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that majority of patients presented were male and had triple vessel disease. Thyroid dysfunction may add to cardiovascular risk and assessment of thyroid function is recommended especially in a high-risk population.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular, heart valve and congenital heart diseases (CHD) constitute a major part of adult and pediatric diseases. In Pakistan, 17% of the adult population suffer from cardiovascular diseases while in the United States of America, Coronary heart disease accounts for one-third of adult deaths. The overall mortality rates from cardiovascular diseases have dropped dramatically in developed countries. Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are among the main causes of premature death and by the year 2030, cardiovascular diseases related mortality is expected to increase up to 25 million, mainly from heart disease and stroke [1].

In addition, cardiovascular diseases are considered the most common cause of hospital admission worldwide resulting in a great economic burden on health care systems. Therefore, prevention of these diseases and early detection of factors that may contribute to their occurrence is considered a public health necessity that should be taken into consideration [2]. A variety of factors may play a role in the development of cardiovascular diseases. These factors can be classified into modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors [3].

The modifiable factors, including smoking, diet and sedentary life, can be prevented and controlled leading to a significant reduction in CVD and associated mortalities. The non-modifiable factors include gender, age, and family history. Thyroid hormones exert a remarkable effect on the cardiovascular system function and cardiac hemodynamic [4]. This effect is more likely to be age-dependent as in certain age groups, thyroid diseases have been suggested to be one of the main cardiovascular risk factors resulting in cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. This reduction in mortality rate is attributed to the improvements in therapy such as preventive measures after Myocardial Infarction (MI), percutaneous interventions (PCI), heart failure therapy and lifestyle modifications such as decreasing risk factors like reduction in total cholesterol, systolic blood pressure, smoking and

physical inactivity. However, contrary to the data from developed countries, cardiovascular mortality rates in countries like the Middle East, India, Pakistan, Latin America, amongst other developing countries, is expected to be high [5].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the patterns of cardiothoracic diseases and procedures in Pakistan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in Ayub medical college during June 2019 to December 2019. Collecting patients' data was conducted through interviewing the patients included in the study and reviewing their medical files. A predesigned questionnaire was used for data collection, and included inquiries about socio-demographic data of the studied patients, smoking, types of cardiovascular diseases and thyroid dysfunction among them.

The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 19. Sample characteristics were summarized as numbers and percentages for qualitative variables. Chi-Square test was used for testing the association between sociodemographic variables, smoking and thyroid dysfunction and pattern of distribution of cardiovascular diseases among the studied population.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 180 patients. There were more females than males. The patients who were younger than 60 years old represented 39.2% of the study population. More than one-third of the individuals (34.3%) were between 60 and 70 years of age, 19.9% were between 70 and 80 years of age, and only 6.6% were older than 80 years. Regarding marital status, 66.3% of the respondents were married, 28.7% were widows, 3.3% were divorced and 1.7 were single. More than two thirds of the respondents were non-smokers and more than one fifth (22.1%) of them were ex-smokers while only 9.4% were current smokers at the time of the study.

Table 01: The relationship between sociodemographic variables, smoking status, and cardiovascular diseases

Variables		Cardiovascular Diseases					Chi-Square	P-value
		Hypertension	Infarction	Ischemia	Arrhythmia	No CVD		
Sex	Female	47 (61.0)	8 (38.1)	5 (31.2)	9 (69.2)	31 (57.4)	8.40	0.078
	Male	30 (39.0)	13 (61.9)	11 (68.8)	4 (30.8)	23 (42.6)		
Age (y)	< 60	25 (32.5)	9 (42.9)	6 (37.5)	6 (46.2)	25 (46.3)	20.88	0.052
	60–70	28 (36.4)	4 (19.0)	4 (25.0)	6 (46.2)	20 (37.0)		
	70–80	18 (23.4)	8 (38.1)	6 (37.5)	0 (0.0)	4 (7.4)		
	> 80	6 (7.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (7.7)	5 (9.3)		
Marital status	Widow	26 (33.8)	4 (19.0)	3 (18.8)	4 (30.8)	15 (27.8)	13.32	0.34
	Single	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (5.6)		
	Married	50 (64.9)	16 (76.2)	13 (81.2)	8 (61.5)	33 (61.1)		
	Divorced	1 (1.3)	1 (4.8)	0 (0.0)	1 (7.7)	3 (5.6)		
Smoking status	Non-smoker	61 (79.2)	11 (52.4)	10 (62.5)	8 (61.5)	34 (63.0)	19.32	0.013
	Smoker	4 (5.2)	5 (23.8)	4 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (7.4)		
	Ex-smoker	12 (15.6)	5 (23.8)	2 (12.5)	5 (38.5)	16 (29.6)		

DISCUSSION:

Analyzing patterns of medical admissions in a hospital is important as it highlights the trends in diseases and serves as a basis for guiding research and important policies. Our study reports the frequency and patterns of cardiovascular diseases presenting to the cardiothoracic ward which require surgical intervention [6]. A study conducted in Karachi to determine the burden of Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD) also found a higher proportion of males suffering from cardiovascular diseases. However, a study done in order to determine the ECG evidence of cardiac ischemia found a higher number of females suffering from IHD [7]. Males are considered to be more at risk for cardiovascular diseases because they are more prone to risk factors such as smoking and alcohol consumption. Yet, the World Health Organization's statistics on the global burden of diseases and related health problems showed increased prevalence among females [8].

Regarding the relation between smoking status and the distribution of cardiovascular diseases in the studied population, smoking status of the studied patients showed a remarkable variation among patients with different cardiovascular disease types with a statistically significant difference which is supported by the findings of another study [9]. Regarding the study limitations, we should say that other factors which may be associated with the pattern of cardiovascular diseases were not covered by the current study focusing on the relation with certain socio-demographic variables, smoking and thyroid dysfunction [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that majority of patients presented were male and had triple vessel disease. Thyroid dysfunction may add to cardiovascular risk and

assessment of thyroid function is recommended especially in a high-risk population. Most of the studied factors had no significant effect on the pattern of the studied cardiovascular diseases and their distribution among the studied population. On the other hand, smoking status of the studied patients showed a remarkable variation among patients with different cardiovascular disease types with a statistically significant difference.

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